

DO PREDICT-EXPLAIN-OBSERVE-EXPLAIN AND VEE HEURISTIC STRATEGIES HAVE THE POTENTIALS TO ELIMINATE GENDER DIFFERENCE IN STUDENTS' ACHIEVEMENT IN ORGANIC CHEMISTRY? A FIELD REPORT

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Abstract

The study investigated if Predict-Explain-Observe-Explain (PEOE) Strategy and Vee Heuristic (VH) Strategy have the potentials to eliminate gender difference in students' achievement in organic chemistry in Ekiti State, Nigeria. The study adopted a pretest, posttest, control group, quasi-experimental research design. The instrument used for data collection was Organic Chemistry Achievement Test (OCAT). Kuder-Richardson (KR-21) formula was used to test internal consistency of OCAT which yielded a reliability value of 0.94. The target population of this study was 14,753 which was the population of Senior Secondary 2 students offering chemistry in study area. A sample of 308 students comprising 174 boys and 134 girls drawn from 9 schools within 9 Local Government Areas (LGA) out of 16 LGA in the Ekiti State, Nigeria selected using multi-stage sampling techniques. Two research questions and two null hypotheses guided the study. The research questions were answered using Mean and Standard Deviation scores while the null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance using Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA). The findings revealed that, there was no significant difference between the mean achievement of male and female students taught Organic Chemistry using PEOE strategy [$F_{1, 101} = .665, P > 0.05$]. The findings also revealed that, there was no significant difference between the mean achievement of male and female students taught Organic Chemistry using VH strategy [$F_{1, 98} = .420, P > 0.050$]. The authors recommended that since PEOE and VH strategies were found to be effective strategies for improving both male and female students' achievement than the use of discussion method; Chemistry teacher's trainee should be trained on the application of PEOE and VH strategies and serving teachers should employ it in teaching to enhance both male and female students' achievement.

Keywords: Gender, achievement, predict-explain-observe-explain and Vee heuristic strategies

Introduction

Science education plays immeasurable role in national development. Perhaps, it is in the recognition of the vital role of science education that science subjects such as chemistry is made a core science subject in Nigeria senior secondary schools. Presently, there seems virtually no science related course of study in the tertiary institutions that does not demand the knowledge of chemistry

in one way or the other. Chemistry is an experimental science that systematically studies the composition, properties and activities of organic and inorganic substances and various elementary forms of matter (Senese, 2013). Organic Chemistry which is the main focus of this study is the scientific study of structure, properties and reactions of organic compounds and organic materials that is matter in its various forms that contain carbon atoms (Ajayi, 2019). It has been

found very useful in different fields of science and technology. It is utilized in petrochemical industries, beverage and alcohol processing production.

Despite the importance of the knowledge of Chemistry in general and Organic chemistry in particular to the society and the effort of the chemistry teachers and researchers to enhance on its teaching and learning, the achievement of both male and female students offering chemistry as measured by their scores in senior secondary school certificate examinations (SSCE) has been very poor. This poor achievement is attested to in West African Examination Council (WAEC) Chief Examiner's report for 2017/2018 session on chemistry result who revealed that students are weak in organic chemistry due to the fact the candidates do not familiarize themselves with the required syllabus and also teachers do not employ effective instructional methods among others. In the same vein, Haruna (2019) investigated the causes of students' poor achievement in SSCE Organic Chemistry concepts. The finding by this author revealed that the ineffective teaching methods such as discussion method employed by secondary school Chemistry teachers are the most recurring causes of students' poor achievement. According to Wilkinson (2016), discussion teaching method is the collaborative exchange of ideas among a teacher and students or among students for the purpose of furthering students thinking, problem solving, and understanding.

Ajayi (2017) noted that discussion method may degenerate into mere talk and may be monopolized by few individuals. This may consequently lead to a conclusion far from the truth even though such may be accepted by the group as a whole. These has led to teachers not exposing the students to meaningful learning and this at the same time has made students to perceive Chemistry

as abstract and difficult concepts to understand. In the long run, learners often resort to memorizing the concepts without meaningful learning taking place. Consequently, the poor achievement of students in chemistry could lead to poor enrolment, students' dropout and could also abort the ambition of many candidates who aspire to study professional courses in higher institutions. Hence, Chemistry teaching can only be result oriented when students are willing and the teachers are favourably disposed to using innovative strategies such as Predict-Explain-Observe-Explain (PEOE) and Vee Heuristic (VH) instructional strategies that have the potentials to equip learners to enhance their learning activities and evaluate the results of these activities that enhanced their conceptual understanding and problem solving abilities.

The technique of Predict-Explain-Observe-Explain (PEOE) was modified from Predict-Observe-Explain (POE) by Rickey and Stacey (2015) to emphasize that the students need to explain their predictions to make their beliefs explicit. POE is a strategy which involves learners in writing down their predictions before doing the activity and the predictions are then followed by an activity in which learners observe their predictions and acclaim on whether or not their predictions were correct or incorrect. In this study, PEOE is an instructional strategy where four or more senior secondary two (SS2) students in a small group setting make predictions for an event and explain the reasons for their predictions, then conduct and observe a laboratory experiment and are required to compare their observations with their predictions, thereby enhancing conceptual understanding of scientific knowledge in Organic Chemistry. Vee heuristic diagram is a V-shaped diagram showing the relationships between conceptual or theoretical and methodological

framework and the resultant knowledge or value claims of a concept.

Vee Heuristic (VH) strategy is a tool that helps in seeing the interplay between what is known and what needs to be known or understood. The Vee heuristic diagram has two sides; The left hand side represents the philosophy, theories, principles and concepts that guide learners in selecting or constructing objects or event and the right hand side highlights the knowledge and value claims as well as data recording and transforming procedures and placed in the middle of the Vee heuristic diagram is the focus questions and events or objects to be observed in the learning process (Gowin, 2010). In this study, VH is an instructional strategy where four or more Senior Secondary two (SS2) students in a small group setting are engaged in coordinated and sustained efforts in the creation of a V-shaped diagram to represent key elements (ideas) that are contained in the structure of knowledge with two sides namely the theoretical (thinking side) on the left and methodological (doing side) on the right in order to monitor their learning activities and evaluate the results of these activities, thereby enhancing conceptual understanding of scientific knowledge in Organic Chemistry. Gender issues in the learning process have continued to engage the interest of researchers in Chemistry because of the achievement differential it exerts on chemistry learning. Conceptually, gender has to do with socially constructed differences which lead to forms of inequality such that the male is regarded as superior and all-knowing and the female as inferior and incompetent. It is a term used to highlight social distinctions between male and female in terms of the position they occupy, the role they play and the social status they have. Gender inequality in chemistry education in general has remained a perennial problem of global scope. The differences between boys

and girls in relation to chemistry education achievement have received a lot of attention in recent years. Some studies indicate that boys achieve better (Gipps, 2014; Kingdon, 2015), either no difference (Teerasong, Chantore, Ruenwongsa, and Nacapricha, 2016; Njue and Magana, 2016; Ajayi & Ogbeba, 2017) or girls outperform boys (Fred, 2011; Soyibo, 2014) have been demonstrated. Studies on gender differences in chemistry achievement continued to yield inconsistent results and it has usually been attributed to unequal exposure of males and females to learning instructions relevant to chemistry learning. Therefore, it is of interest to find out if Predict-Explain-Observe-Explain and Vee Heuristic Strategies do influence gender difference in students' achievement in Organic Chemistry in Ekiti State, Nigeria. The purpose of this study was to investigate if Predict-Explain-Observe-Explain (PEOE) and Vee Heuristic (VH) strategies have the potentials to eliminate gender difference in students' achievement in organic chemistry in Ekiti State, Nigeria. Specifically, the study establishes: if there is any difference in the effect of PEOE strategy on male and female students' mean achievement scores in Organic Chemistry. It also investigated the difference in the effect of VH strategy on male and female students' mean achievement scores in Organic Chemistry.

Research Questions

To achieve the purposes of the study, the authors answered the following questions:

1. What is the difference in the mean achievement scores between male and female students taught Organic Chemistry using PEOE strategy?
2. What is the difference in the mean achievement scores between male and female students taught Organic Chemistry using VH strategy?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance:

- a. The difference in the mean achievement scores of male and female students taught Organic Chemistry using PEOE strategy is not statistically significant
- b. There is no significant difference between the mean achievement scores of male and female students taught Organic Chemistry using VH strategy

Research Design and Procedure

The study adopted a quasi-experimental non-randomized pre-test, post-test control group design. This design was adopted because it is not possible to have complete randomization of the subject as this may disrupt school organization. The study area was Ekiti State, Nigeria. The target population of this study was 14,753 being the population of Senior Secondary 2 (SS2) students offering chemistry in the study area. A sample of 308 students comprising 174 boys and 134 girls drawn from 9 schools within 9 Local Government Areas (LGA) out of 16 LGA in the Ekiti State, Nigeria was selected using multi-stage sampling techniques. An instrument known as Organic Chemistry Achievement Test (OCAT) was used for data collection. OCAT was adopted from West African Examination Council (WAEC) past examination question papers of 2003-2018. OCAT items were based on WAEC, which is standardized, since the target of the study was to enhance the students' achievement, at this level. The test instrument consisted of two sections. Section A consisted of the respondents' bio-data, while section B consisted of 40 structured multiple choice objective items with four options (A, B, C, D) drawn from the concepts of organic chemistry to which respondents

provide the answers by selecting the correct option.

However, standardized tests do have environmental, regional and sociological sensitivity, as such, the items were face validated by presenting them to three experts in Science Education and one lecturer that is knowledgeable in measurement and evaluation in the Department of Curriculum and Teaching, Benue State University, Makurdi and one expert in testing and measurement in the College of Agricultural and Science Education, Department of Educational Foundations and General Studies, Federal University of Agriculture, Makurdi. The experts were asked to assess the instrument in terms of scope of coverage, content relevance, ambiguity, and vagueness of expression. Corrections and suggestions arising from these experts were used to review the instrument and the instructional packages. Organic Chemistry Achievement Test (OCAT) upon validation was trial-tested to establish the reliability of the instrument. Kuder-Richardson (KR-21) formula was used to establish the internal consistency of OCAT with a reliability value of 0.94.

Prior to actual treatment, one week for the training of the Chemistry teachers who served as research assistants was done. Intact classes were assigned to experimental and control groups after which Organic Chemistry Achievement Test (OCAT) was administered as pre-test with the assistance of the sampled schools' Chemistry teachers. This lasted for one week before actual teaching commences. During lessons, the teachers taught the experimental group I and experimental group II Organic Chemistry topics using predict-explain-observe-explain and Vee heuristic instructional strategy respectively in line with lessons procedures prepared. The control group was also taught the same Organic Chemistry topics using the discussion lesson plans. This lasted for six weeks. At the end of these actual teaching

periods, the pre-OCAT was reshuffled and administered as post-test which lasted for one week and the post test was marked by the research assistants using the marking scheme developed by the researcher. The pre-test score constituted the covariant of the post-test scores. Mean and Standard Deviation scores were used to answer the research questions while Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) was used to test the null hypotheses.

Results and Findings

Presentations in this section are based on research questions and null hypotheses

Research Question One

What is the difference in the mean achievement scores between male and female students taught Organic Chemistry using PEOE strategy? The answer to research question one is contained on Table 1.

Table 1: Mean Achievement and Standard Deviation Scores of Male and Female Students taught Organic Chemistry using PEOE strategy

Group	Gender	N	PRE- OCAT		POST- OCAT		Mean Gain within Gender
			\bar{x}	δ	\bar{x}	δ	
PEOE strategy	Male	61	10.23	3.41	29.67	5.27	19.44
	Female	43	10.21	2.97	28.81	5.53	18.60
Mean diff. between Gender			0.02		0.86		0.84

Source: Field Survey, 2019

Table 1 reveals the mean achievement and standard deviation scores of male and female students taught Organic Chemistry using Predict-Explain-Observe-Explain (PEOE) strategy. The data in table 1 showed that the pre-test mean scores for male and female were 10.23 and 10.21 respectively with their standard deviation scores of 3.41 and 2.97 respectively while the post-test mean scores were 29.67 and 28.81 respectively with their standard deviation scores of 5.27 and 5.53 respectively. The mean difference of both

sexes was 0.84. This difference though small is in favour of the male students. This implies that male students achieved slightly higher than their female counterparts using PEOE strategy.

Research Question Two

What is the difference in the mean achievement scores between male and female students taught Organic Chemistry using VH strategy? The answer to research question two is contained on Table 2.

Table 2: Mean Achievement and Standard Deviation Scores of Male and Female Students taught Organic Chemistry using VH strategy

Group	Gender	N	PRE- OCAT		POST- OCAT		Mean Gain within Gender
			\bar{x}	δ	\bar{x}	δ	
VH strategy	Male	56	10.23	3.64	28.21	5.25	17.98
	Female	45	10.07	2.66	27.53	5.02	17.46
Mean diff. between Gender			0.16		0.68		0.52

Source: Field Survey, 2019

Table 2 reveals the mean achievement and standard deviation scores of male and female students taught Organic Chemistry using Vee Heuristic (VH) strategy. The data in table 2 showed that the pre-test mean scores for male and female were 10.23 and 10.07 respectively with their standard deviation scores of 3.64 and 2.66 respectively while the post-test mean scores were 28.21 and 27.53 respectively with their standard deviation scores of 5.25 and 5.02 respectively. The mean difference of both sexes was 0.52. This difference though small

is in favour of the male students. This implies that male students achieved slightly higher than their female counterparts using VH strategy.

Hypothesis One

The difference in the mean achievement scores of male and female students taught Organic Chemistry using PEOE strategy is not statistically significant. The data for analysis of hypothesis one is contained on Table 3.

Table 3: Summary of ANCOVA Result for Achievement of Male and Female Students taught Organic Chemistry using PEOE Strategy

Source	Type III sum of squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Partial Eta Squared
Corrected model	903.799 ^a	2	451.899	22.127	.000	.305
Intercept	3770.959	1	3770.959	184.642	.000	.646
TPrOCAT	885.224	1	885.224	43.344	.000	.300
Gender	13.589	1	13.589	.665	.417	.007
Error	2062.730	101	20.423			
Total	92355.000	104				
Corrected Total	2966.529	103				

a. R squared = .305 (Adjusted R Squared= .291)

Source: Field Survey, 2019

ANCOVA Test result in Table 3 reveals that there is no significant difference between the mean achievement of male and female students taught Organic Chemistry using

Predict-Explain-Observe-Explain (PEOE) strategy [$F_{1, 101}=.665, P>0.05$]. The null hypothesis is therefore not rejected. This means that PEOE strategy enhanced both male

and female students' achievement in Organic Chemistry. Meanwhile, the effect size was 0.007 as indicated by the corresponding partial eta squared value which Cohen (1988) in Pallant (2014) considered as small effect size. This implies that, only 0.7% of the difference in the achievement scores of male and female students taught Organic Chemistry was explained by PEOE. Hence, the difference in the achievement scores of male and female students taught Organic Chemistry using

PEOE strategy has very small statistical effect size.

Hypothesis Two

There is no significant difference between the mean achievement scores of male and female students taught Organic Chemistry using VH strategy. The summary of analysis of hypothesis two is contained on Table 4.

Table 4: Summary of ANCOVA Result for Achievement of Male and Female Students taught Organic Chemistry using VH Strategy

Source	Type III sum of squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Partial Eta Squared
Corrected model	15.224 ^a	2	7.612	.284	.753	.006
Intercept	6811.882	1	6811.882	254.507	.000	.722
TPrOCAT	3.655	1	3.655	.137	.713	.001
Gender	11.231	1	11.231	.420	.519	.004
Error	2622.974	98	26.765			
Total	81319.000	101				
Corrected Total	2638.198	100				

a. R squared = .006 (Adjusted R Squared= -.015)

Source: Field Survey, 2019

ANCOVA Test result in Table 4 reveals that there is no significant difference between the mean achievement of male and female students taught Organic Chemistry using Vee Heuristic (VH) strategy [$F_{1, 98} = .420, P > 0.05$]. The null hypothesis is therefore not rejected. This means that VH strategy enhanced both male and female students' achievement in Organic Chemistry. Meanwhile, the effect size was 0.004 which Cohen (1988) in Pallant (2014) considered as very small effect size. This implies that, only 0.4% of the difference in the achievement scores of male and female students taught Organic Chemistry was explained by VH strategy. Hence, the difference in the achievement scores of male and female students taught Organic Chemistry using VH strategy has small statistical effect size.

Discussion of Findings

The study investigated if Predict-Explain-Observe-Explain (PEOE) Strategy and Vee Heuristic (VH) Strategy have the potentials to eliminate gender difference in students' achievement in organic chemistry in Ekiti State, Nigeria. The study findings revealed that male students achieved slightly higher than their female counterparts using Predict-Explain-Observe-Explain (PEOE) strategy but ANCOVA test showed that the difference was not significant. This implies that, the difference in the achievement of male and female students taught Organic Chemistry using PEOE strategy was not statistically significant. This means that PEOE strategy enhanced both male and female students' achievement in Organic Chemistry This finding agrees with those of Teerasong, Chantore, Ruenwongsa, and Nacapricha (2016) and Ajayi and Ogbeba (2017) who

found that PEOE approach and activity-based strategy facilitated students' achievements in Biology regardless of gender in Public Secondary Schools in Kenya and Nigeria respectively. However, the finding contradicts the finding of Kingdon (2015) who found that male students' had higher interest than their female counterparts in Physics using Predict-Observe-Explain (POE). However, the likely explanation for this outcome may be attributed to the fact that PEOE used to help both male and female students develop a cognitive structure that enable meaningful learning.

The study also revealed that male students achieved slightly higher than their female counterparts using Vee Heuristic strategy (VH) strategy but ANCOVA test showed that the difference was not significant. This implies that, the difference in the achievement of male and female students taught Organic Chemistry using VH strategy was not statistically significant. This means that VH strategy enhanced both male and female students' achievement in Organic Chemistry. This finding agrees with those of Njue and Magana (2016) who found that Vee heuristic teaching approach facilitated students' achievements in Biology regardless of gender in Public Secondary Schools in Kenya. However, the finding contradicts the finding of Fred (2011) and Soyibo (2014) who found that female students' had higher achievement than their male counterparts in Biology and Elementary Science using VH strategy. However, the likely explanation for this outcome may be attributed to the fact that VH strategy is used to enable students to understand the structure of knowledge and process of knowledge construction. Therefore, if VH strategy is implemented in classroom, it will enable male and female students to understand how concepts and processes are meaningfully learning because its purpose is to interplay between what is familiar and what they are yet to be known or understood in

Chemistry in general and Organic Chemistry in particular. Thus, if either Predict-Explain-Observe-Explain or Vee Heuristic strategy is implemented in chemistry classroom, it will enhance the teaching and learning of Chemistry in general and Organic Chemistry in particular, thereby enhancing both male and female students' achievement in Chemistry in improving candidates' performance in external examinations such as West African Examination Council (WAEC) and National Examinations Council (NECO).

Conclusion and Recommendations

It is evident from the findings of this study that the use of both Predict-Explain-Observe-Explain (PEOE) strategy and Vee heuristic (VH) strategy enhanced both male and female students' achievement in Organic chemistry. In other words, no gender disparity exists in the achievement of male and female students taught Organic Chemistry using PEOE and VH instructional strategies respectively. This implies that both PEOE and VH strategies are very rewarding to students' in-terms of achievement regardless of gender. Based on the findings and conclusion of this study, the following recommendations were made:

1. Chemistry teacher's trainee should be train on the application of Predict-Explain-Observe-Explain (PEOE) strategy and Vee heuristic (VH) strategy and serving teachers should employ the use of PEOE and VH strategies in teaching to enhance both male and female students' achievement in Organic Chemistry.
2. PEOE and VH instructional strategies are not gender sensitive therefore both male and female students should be involved in PEOE and VH activities to enhance their achievement in Organic Chemistry.

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